

The Variational Version of Riemann Hypothesis

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July 28, 2025

Abstract

In this paper, We suggest a new formulation of the Riemann Hypothesis as a variational problem in an appropriately defined function space F by associating each element $f \in F$ with a functional $\varepsilon(f)$ (we call it energy functional), such that $\varepsilon(f) = 0$ if and only if the real parts of the zeros of the function f equal $\frac{1}{2}$. In this framework, we prove that Riemann Hypothesis is true if and only if Riemann zeta function is the unique solution of two partial differential equations which appear as a result of minimizing the energy functional.

1 Introduction

In the early 19th century, mathematicians were trying to understand the behavior of prime numbers. Gauss [1] and Legendre [2] proposed a formula for the number of primes less than a given number. In this context, Riemann studied his famous function (the Riemann zeta function), focusing particularly on the zeros of this function (which are closely related to the distribution of prime numbers). Riemann noticed that the functional equation of his function imposes a symmetry around a critical line, and when he calculated some non-trivial zeros, he found that they indeed lie on this line. From this, Riemann conjectured that all non-trivial zeros lie exactly on the critical line [3,5].

There are several approaches to dealing with this conjecture, including trying to prove it through the structure of the Riemann zeta function itself, trying to arrive at knowledge of the zeros by studying the numerical behavior of functions related to the distribution of prime numbers [4,7]. For another approaches see [8,9].

In this paper, we tried to think about this issue from a different point of view. We consider the Riemann zeta function to be an object that lives in a space \mathcal{F} of functions that has the same basic properties as the zeta function. We considered that there is a measure of the extent to which the zeros of the function $f \in \mathcal{F}$ deviate from the critical line, which we called the "energy of the function" denoted by $\mathcal{E}[f]$, such that the statement "Riemann hypothesis is true", is equivalent to the statement that the "energy of the Riemann zeta function equal zero". In this context, we derive two differential equations as a result of the

"minimum energy" condition $E[f] = 0$, and therefore Riemann hypothesis is true iff the Riemann zeta function is the unique solution to these two equations. For some applications of differential equations see [6].

2 Definition of the Function Space \mathcal{F}

We define a class of complex-valued functions $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, denoted by \mathcal{F} , as the functions which have the following properties,

1- Analytic Structure and Meromorphy

We require that each function $f \in \mathcal{F}$ is meromorphic on the entire complex plane \mathbb{C} . It has a simple pole at $s = 1$, and is analytic on the critical strip $0 < \Re(s) < 1$ except for the isolated zeros and poles.

2-Dirichlet Series Representation

For all $f \in \mathcal{F}$, there exists a sequence of complex coefficients $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ such that:

$$f(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{a_n}{n^s},$$

which converges absolutely in the half-plane $\Re(s) > 1$.

3- Functional Equation of Zeta Type

Define the completed function associated to f as:

$$\xi_f(s) := \pi^{-s/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) f(s).$$

This completed function $\xi_f(s)$ is required to be an entire function. This implies that the poles of the Gamma function at $s = 0, -2, -4, \dots$ are cancelled by simple zeros of $f(s)$ at these points. We impose the reflection symmetry, which is extended by analytic continuation to all of \mathbb{C} :

$$\xi_f(s) = \xi_f(1 - s), \quad \forall s \in \mathbb{C}.$$

4- Real-Valuedness on the Real Axis

To preserve real structure and enable reality constraints on the coefficients a_n , we assume:

$$f(s) \in \mathbb{R}, \quad \forall s \in (1, \infty).$$

5- Growth Condition (Order ≤ 1)

The function f must be of finite exponential type. Specifically, we require:

$$|f(s)| \leq C(1 + |s|)^A e^{B|s|}, \quad \text{for some constants } A, B > 0,$$

which ensures that f is an entire function (up to its pole) of order at most 1. This is necessary for applying Hadamard factorization theorem later.

Notice that these properties together ensure that the space \mathcal{F} includes the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(s)$, and remains constrained enough to enable a well-defined energy functional and a unique flow limit (as we see later).

3 Energy Functional $E[f]$

Let $f \in \mathcal{F}$, and let $\mathcal{Z}(f) \subset \mathbb{C}$ is the multiset of nontrivial zeros of f , counted with multiplicity and excluding any trivial or symmetry-induced zeros (e.g., those imposed by the functional equation).

To define a kind of "deviation" of the nontrivial zeros from the critical line $\text{Re}(s) = \frac{1}{2}$, we define the **energy functional** as follow:

$$E[f] := \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^1 W(\alpha, \tau) (\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^4 \left| \left(\frac{f'}{f} (\alpha + i\tau) \right) \right|^2 d\alpha d\tau, \quad (1)$$

where, $W(\alpha, \tau) = \sin(\pi\alpha) \exp^{-c\tau^2}$, c is greater than zero.

Theorem 1 $E[f] = 0 \Leftrightarrow$ all zeros and poles of $f(s)$ in the critical strip lie on the critical line.

Proof. First direction: $E[f] = 0 \Rightarrow$ all zeros and poles of $f(s)$ in the critical strip lie on the critical line

Assume that we have $E[f] = 0$ and assume that there exists a nontrivial zero or pole at $s_0 = \alpha_0 + i\tau_0$ with $\alpha_0 \in (0, \frac{1}{2}) \cup (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$. I. e., the singularity is not on the critical line.

Now, the energy functional is defined as:

$$E[f] = \iint_{\Omega} I(\alpha, \tau) d\alpha d\tau = 0, \quad \Omega = (0, 1) \times (-\infty, \infty), \quad (2)$$

where

$$I(\alpha, \tau) = W(\alpha, \tau) (\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^4 \left| \left(\frac{f'}{f} (\alpha + i\tau) \right) \right|^2.$$

Now, Let D_ε be a small disk of radius ε (small enough) centered at s_0 , such that D_ε contain no other zeros or poles of f . (We can do this since the zeros and poles are isolated. Now, notice that

1- Both $W(\alpha, \tau) = \sin(\pi\alpha)e^{-c\tau^2}$ and $(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^4$ is strictly positive in $D_\varepsilon \setminus \{s_0\}$ [since $\alpha_0 \neq \frac{1}{2}$].

2- $\left| \frac{f'}{f} \right|^2$ is strictly positive since it has a pole at s_0 and is well-behaved elsewhere in the disk, so we can conclude that:

$$I(\alpha, \tau) > 0 \text{ on } D_\varepsilon \setminus \{s_0\},$$

but then in this case we have,

$$E[f] = \iint_{\Omega} I(\alpha, \tau) d\alpha d\tau \geq \iint_{D_\varepsilon} I(\alpha, \tau) d\alpha d\tau > 0,$$

and this contradict our assumption that $E[f] = 0$. This complete the first direction.

Second direction: all zeros and poles of $f(s)$ in the critical strip lie on the critical line $\Rightarrow E[f] = 0$.

Assume that all nontrivial zeros $Z(f)$ and poles $P(f)$ of $f(s)$ are located on the critical line. i.e, , for every zero or pole $\rho \in Z(f) \cup P(f)$, we have $\Re(\rho) = \frac{1}{2}$.

The core of the proof of this direction relies on a fundamental principle from measure theory, that is a non negative function has zero integral if and only if the

function itself is zero almost everywhere, so if we can prove that $I(\alpha, \tau) = W(\alpha, \tau)(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^4 \left| \left(\frac{f'}{f}(\alpha + i\tau) \right) \right|^2$ is zero almost everywhere, then we done.

Let $\rho_0 = \frac{1}{2} + i\tau_0$ be a simple zero of $f(s)$. Near the zero, so we can write :

$$f(s) = c(s - \rho_0) + \mathcal{O}((s - \rho_0)^2),$$

for some constant $c \neq 0$. Hence

$$\frac{f'}{f}(s) = \frac{1}{s - \rho_0} + \text{analytic terms.}$$

Let $s = \alpha + i\tau$, then we have:

$$\left| \frac{f'}{f}(s) \right|^2 \sim \frac{1}{(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^2 + (\tau - \tau_0)^2},$$

so, the integrand behaves like:

$$I(\alpha, \tau) \approx W(\alpha, \tau)(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^4 \cdot \frac{1}{(\alpha - \frac{1}{2})^2 + (\tau - \tau_0)^2}.$$

As $(\alpha, \tau) \rightarrow (\frac{1}{2}, \tau_0)$, we have:

$$\lim_{(\alpha, \tau) \rightarrow (\frac{1}{2}, \tau_0)} I(\alpha, \tau) = 0.$$

This argument applies to all isolated zeros and poles on the critical line, and since they are countable, they form a set of measure zero, so $I(\alpha, \tau) = 0$ almost everywhere.

Now, since $I(\alpha, \tau) \geq 0$ and zero almost everywhere, it follows by measure theory that:

$$E[f] = \iint_{\Omega} I(\alpha, \tau) d\alpha d\tau = 0,$$

where $\Omega = (0, 1) \times (-\infty, \infty)$. This completes the proof. ■

4 The Functional and the Variation

Now, we want to find the function $f(s)$ that minimizes the functional $E[f]$ defined on the domain $\Omega = (0, 1) \times (-\infty, \infty)$ in the complex plane, where $s = \alpha + i\tau$. Remember that $E[f] = \iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \left|\frac{f'}{f}\right|^2 d\alpha d\tau$, where f' denotes the derivative of $f(s)$ with respect to s , and $W(\alpha, \tau) = \sin(\pi\alpha)e^{-c\tau^2}$.

To find the stationary points of the functional, we introduce a small variation to the function $f(s)$. Let $f_{\epsilon}(s)$ be a family of functions parameterized by a small real number ϵ , defined as:

$$f_{\epsilon}(s) := f(s) + \epsilon g(s)$$

where $g(s)$ is an analytic test function with compact support on the domain Ω . The derivative of f_{ϵ} is then $f'_{\epsilon} = f' + \epsilon g'$.

Recall that the condition for a stationary point is that the first variation of the functional with respect to ϵ must be zero, i.e.,

$$\delta E = \frac{d}{d\epsilon} E[f_{\epsilon}]|_{\epsilon=0} = 0,$$

Now, we have:

$$\frac{d}{d\epsilon} E[f_{\epsilon}] = \iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \left|\frac{f'_{\epsilon}}{f_{\epsilon}}\right|^2 d\alpha d\tau.$$

We now evaluate $\frac{d}{d\epsilon} \left|\frac{f'_{\epsilon}}{f_{\epsilon}}\right|^2$. Let us focus on it.

Let us define

$$Z_{\epsilon} := \frac{f'_{\epsilon}}{f_{\epsilon}} = \frac{f' + \epsilon g'}{f + \epsilon g}.$$

We know that $\left|\frac{f'_{\epsilon}}{f_{\epsilon}}\right|^2 = |Z_{\epsilon}|^2 = Z_{\epsilon} \overline{Z_{\epsilon}}$, so we have:

$$\frac{d}{d\epsilon} \left|\frac{f'_{\epsilon}}{f_{\epsilon}}\right|^2 = \frac{d}{d\epsilon} |Z_{\epsilon}|^2 = \frac{dZ_{\epsilon}}{d\epsilon} \overline{Z_{\epsilon}} + Z_{\epsilon} \frac{d\overline{Z_{\epsilon}}}{d\epsilon}.$$

For $\frac{dZ_{\epsilon}}{d\epsilon}$, we have:

$$\frac{dZ_{\epsilon}}{d\epsilon} = \frac{(g')(f + \epsilon g) - (f' + \epsilon g')(g)}{(f + \epsilon g)^2} = \frac{g'f - f'g}{(f + \epsilon g)^2},$$

so we have:

$$\frac{dZ_{\epsilon}}{d\epsilon}|_{\epsilon=0} = \frac{g'f - f'g}{(f + g)^2}.$$

Also, we have by a direct computation that Z_{ϵ} at $\epsilon = 0$ is $Z_0 = \frac{f'}{f}$, so finally we have

$$\frac{d}{d\epsilon} \left| \frac{f_\epsilon}{f'_\epsilon} \right|^2 = \left(\frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2} \right) \cdot \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} + \overline{\left(\frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{f'}{f} \right).$$

Now, the stationarity condition integral becomes,

$$\iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \left[\left(\frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2} \right) \cdot \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} + \overline{\left(\frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{f'}{f} \right) \right] d\alpha d\tau = 0$$

Now, notice that $\frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2}$ is the Wirtinger derivative of $\frac{g}{f}$, i.e.,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) = \frac{g'f - f'g}{(f)^2}.$$

Recall that

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} - i \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{s}} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} + i \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau}.$$

So, we can rewrite the stationarity condition integral as follow:

$$\iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) \cdot \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} + \overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right)} \cdot \left(\frac{f'}{f} \right) \right] d\alpha d\tau = 0$$

Now, recall Green's Identity in the complex analysis,

$$\iint_{\Omega} A \frac{\partial G}{\partial s} d\alpha d\tau = - \iint_{\Omega} A \frac{\partial G}{\partial \bar{s}} d\alpha d\tau + \oint_{\partial\Omega} AG d\bar{s}$$

Now, we rewrite stationarity condition integral as follow

$$\iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} \right] d\alpha d\tau + \iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right)} \left(\frac{f'}{f} \right) d\alpha d\tau = 0$$

We now focus on the first term,

$$\iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) \right] \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} d\alpha d\tau.$$

Using Green's Identity, we put $A = W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)}$, $G = \frac{g}{f}$, and since we choose that g and there for G as an analytic test function with compact support on the domain Ω ., the boundary integral term vanishes.

So, for the first term, we have:

$$\iint_{\Omega} W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) \right] \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} d\alpha d\tau = - \iint_{\Omega} \left(\frac{g}{f} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left[W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2} \right)^4 \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f} \right)} \right] d\alpha d\tau$$

So, we arrive at the first differential equation as follow:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial s}[(W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)}] = 0, \quad (3)$$

and by the same procedure to the second term, we use $A = W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)$, $G = \overline{\frac{g}{f}}$, and remember that $\overline{\frac{\partial}{\partial s}\left(\frac{g}{f}\right)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{s}}\left(\overline{\frac{g}{f}}\right)$, we arrive at the second differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{s}}[(W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)] = 0, \quad (4)$$

Summary 2 *The Riemann Hypothesis is true if and only if the Riemann zeta function is the unique solution to the following two partial differential equations, within the function space F :*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial s}[(W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \overline{\left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)}] &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{s}}[(W(\alpha, \tau) \left(\alpha - \frac{1}{2}\right)^4 \left(\frac{f'}{f}\right)] &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

this is because that these two equations are a result of the "minimum energy" condition $E[f] = 0$. Therefore, proving that the Riemann zeta function is the unique solution to these two equations is a direct proof of the Riemann Hypothesis.

References

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